

Skills 4 eosc

D6.2 Starter kits for professional networks: generic

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable is an Open Science starter kit developed to provide support the creation of new professional and sustainable communities. Professional communities play a key role in the context of Skills4EOSC Competence Centre network as they are seen as a tool for lifelong learning through peers. This is a generic starter kit.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
Community	A mutually supportive, self-perpetuating group with purpose and structure.
Community Canvas	A framework designed to help build and run a new community, or analyse and improve an existing one by identifying fundamental themes of identity, experience, and structure.
Community of Practice	A group who shares a common concern, set of problems, or interest in a topic and who come together to fulfil individual and group goals.
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement
CSCCE Community Participation Model	A framework for modes of member engagement occurring in a community: convey/consume, collaborate, co-create, and outside of it: champion.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FRDN	Flemish Research Data Network
INOSC	International Network of Open Science and Scholarship Communities
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillsets
RDA	Research Data Alliance
CSCCE Community Participation Model	A framework for modes of member engagement occurring in a community: convey/consume, collaborate, co-create, and outside of it: champion.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
INOSC	International Network of Open Science and Scholarship Communities

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Network	Expansive open chains of connections, without having a concept of membership, and little expectation of mutually supportive interaction
Onboarding	Process of inviting and welcoming people, including information about expectations and norms around participation.
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
Scaffolding	Supportive information, activities, and processes that address barriers to participation and ensure all can access and engage.

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1 Summary for starting and sustaining a community.

Theme	Actions
Aim:	Help create or sustain communities in Open Science for researchers and research support staff.
Pillars:	<p>Interaction: through communication or collaborative activity building relationships between participants.</p> <p>Common domain of interest to define identity: Open Science , or elements of Open Science practice.</p> <p>Domains best suited are “problematic”. Things attracting discussion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Might not have consensus. • Contain dilemmas. • Have no idea on how to address. <p>Identity implies commitment and shared competence. Formal or informal identity defines entry to domain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common location • Professional qualification or job titles? • Interest <p>Shared experience: Members as practitioners directly sharing experiences, or using common tools, facing similar challenges, can all be part of this element.</p> <p>Support for in-person activities and for time leaders and/or champions spend on it.</p>

	Aims and objectives of a community can shift and evolve in time depending on the membership.
<i>Benefits:</i>	<p>Amplifying concerns: “We are worried about...”</p> <p>Building arguments: “How can we push back against the argument that...”</p> <p>Documenting: “How did we manage (or here is how others managed) to do something...”</p> <p>Identifying gaps: “There is no community that brings together data protection officers and repository managers.”</p> <p>Problem solving: “How do we get researchers publish Open Access?”</p> <p>Requesting information: “What kind of journal policies on data sharing are in place?”</p> <p>Reusing assets: “This is a great tool for making data FAIR...”</p> <p>Seeking experience: “This person has managed to do...”</p> <p>Shaping roles: “What does it mean to be a...”</p> <p>Sharing opportunities: “Here is a job at...”</p> <p>Visits: Going to learn from others.</p>
<i>Responsibilities:</i>	Some level of coordination and decision making is needed, even if small and voluntary, to guide and focus on tasks and organisation:

	<p>Manage Information and knowledge about the community and ensuring people can access it or information referenced by the community.</p> <p>Facilitate meetings: making sure meetings remain focused, setting agenda, ensuring participants can contribute.</p> <p>Manage relationships: strengthening and building relationships within the community, identifying, and recruiting new members, and helping them move to more active roles.</p> <p>Organise subject matter experts with knowledge relevant to the field or topic.</p> <p>Find, manage, and maintain access to technology platforms to manage information and allow people to participate.</p> <p>Help maintain and grow/evolve through crafting strategic plans.</p> <p>Be open to discuss redefining the scope of the community when or if needed.</p>
<p><i>Practical actions:</i></p>	<p>Define why the community should exist and who it is for.</p> <p>Think about models and theory in the context of need and who would be involved.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community of Practice • CCSE • Community Canvas <p>Identify interaction processes: what are common interest(s)? What can participants share?</p> <p>What benefits result for participants, community, and wider domain?</p>

Scope roles for managing and championing.

Positionality, Charter, and Code of Conduct: Short, simple, should help shape and direction. Address:

- Purpose
- Eligibility
- Objectives and targets
- Expectations on behaviour, like commitment to collaboration, expectations on privacy and confidentiality.

Time (funding) needed for leads and champions.

“Skills wheel” to identify skills required, assist professional development, or allocate skills effectively. At an organisational level, it supports gap analyses of the skills across the group.

Launch: to start meeting regularly and help forge an identity. Consider choice: in-person, online, or both.

Promotion to target communities:

- Discussion channels (email, slack, discord)
- Materials: can range from promotional to research articles.
- Newsletter
- Social media
- Conferences: Targeting to present or organising own.

Think about “on” and “offboarding”: How people join and leave the community.

2 Introduction

2.1 Executive summary

The growth of Open Science initiatives in research, allied to the expansion of Open Data initiatives, requires considered management of the research processes and research data to ensure it is transparent and accessible.

A range of professional identities have emerged to help this, from within research and research support, in conceptualising, collecting, documenting, analysing, sharing, publishing, and preserving research and its associated outputs for transparency and responsible and efficient sharing.

But these professional identities, defined responsibilities, roles, perceived organisational value, as well as required knowledge and skills, can vary.

One way to help develop skills and knowledge is to build Open Science communities that share experiences, collaborate on problems, and co-create solutions.

This starter kit is designed to help. It borrows from three models of community organisation to help with the identification of a need for an Open Science community, or community focusing on an aspect of Open Science, then the practical steps and conceptual thinking needed to launch and sustain a community. Kits also build upon the existing International Network of Open Science and Scholarship Communities (INOSC) Open Science Community Starter Kit (Brinkman and Eerland, 2022). Reference is also made to approaches from social psychology and management theory on group dynamics and effective team building.

The starter kit is not intended to be too proscriptive. It acknowledges there is variation in the size, scope, and geographical spread of potential communities and this means variation in elements of organisation. But it does ask for thinking critically about some of those aspects to ensure they are appropriate to the needs of a community and facilitate its aims and objectives.

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By helping the establishment and sustaining of communities this toolkit contributes to Open Science initiatives.

It also contributes to the Skills4EOSC aim to develop common activities and training resources for collaborative and reliable support to the European Open Science Cloud aim of providing reliable research data. Moreover, professional networks play a key role in the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network. Professional networks are linked to the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres as they include professionals who share interests, goals, and values related to OS principles and practices and they can be seen as a key tool to implement lifelong learning through peer support.

In the broader European Open Science and EOSC context, some networks are pre-existing to the Skills4EOSC activities, while the project intends to support building new ones via its Competence Centre Network.

This Starter Kit provides a link in Skills4EOSC Work Package 6 between tasks to identify existing professional communities and networks (T6.1) and instigate and sustain ones for data stewards, researchers, and thematic experts. It also paves the way for Skills4EOSC Work Package 7 activities that will shape the relationship between Competence Centres and Professional Networks and Communities and their respective roles in the training and support context.

The community approach allows learning to be embedded and sustained within the daily Open Science workflows of researchers and research support, based at institutions, and within thematic networks identified by Skills4EOSC (T6.3.1, T6.3.2), as well as other professionals such as museum curators (T6.3.3).

2.1.1 How to use this Open Science network starter kit

If you are looking to set up a new one...

Section 3 is the place to start.

Section 3 can help you conceptualise what a community is, using existing models of community organisation, and how they can help individual and collective professional development.

Section 3 also helps identify responsibility roles within the community.

Section 4 will look at the work you should do leading up to that first meeting of the group, including planning and organisational tasks.

If you are looking to sustain or grow an existing community...

Section 5 can help.

This looks at sustaining a community, including growing membership, encouraging participation, welcoming new members, and saying goodbye to others.

At the start of each section is a set of summary practical actions.

You can refer to them to either get an overview of what is in that section, or look at them to identify and reinforce practical steps outlined in the section.

Section 1 provides a two page overview of all the practical actions in this starter kit.

In this starter kit you will find guidance on establishing and sustaining professional communities for data stewards.

In summary, it:

- Elaborates on benefits, including sharing expertise, solving common problems, advancing the profession, building tools, and collaborating.
- Borrows from [Communities of Practice](#), the [CSCCE Community Participation Model](#), and the [Community Canvas](#) approach.
- Discusses leadership responsibilities, including managing information and relationships, facilitating discussions, organising subject matter experts, and finding and managing platforms.
- Presents practical actions to consider, like defining purpose and audience, considering models and approaches (community or networks), writing a charter and code of conduct, identifying leads and champions, launching with a kick-off event, and promoting the community.
- Looks at sustaining actions including welcoming new members, enabling participation through “scaffolding”, and planning for members leaving the community.

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- Discusses various levels of participation, from core to peripheral. In sum, a mix is healthy, but imbalance can create problems.
- Presents case studies as examples of existing data steward communities like the [Flemish Research Data Network \(FRDN\)](#) and the [rOpenSci](#).

3 Getting started

Key actions: determine purpose and approach, identify benefits and responsibilities, use existing models/tools to help plan and organise launch.

3.1 Practical actions: Introduction

- **Identify a domain of interest** that connects members.
- **Recognise existing communities or networks** that may already exist among groups with shared interests or experiences.
- **Community or network?** Define the purpose and scope. Decide if it will be a community focused on mutual support and shared values, or a looser network for sharing information.
- **Articulate benefits** a community can provide, like sharing knowledge, solving problems, advocating for issues, and learning from each other.
- **Read up on models** like [Community of Practice](#), [Community Participation Model](#), and [Community Canvas](#) to help focus planning on launch, growth, and sustainability of a community.
- **Scope key roles** and responsibilities like leads, champions, facilitators, and experts that will be necessary to manage and grow the group.
- **Consider responsibilities and policies** to manage information, facilitate discussions, build relationships, and provide subject matter expertise.

3.2 Starter kit

Communities work to develop Open Science and research data sharing through mutual learning, shared expertise, and collaborating to solve common problems in their communities.

Through collaboration and sharing, communities are emerging and growing in areas related to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This includes Research Data Management (RDM) (including data curators, data librarians and other data professionals), Open Science communities at institutional, regional, cross-national, and European levels, as well as thematic

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communities, like, for example, AI, health and technology research, and museum curators.

They can be open to anyone working in, or interested in, its domain. This can bring together like-minded, and non-like-minded people, in terms of their beliefs, experiences, and professional roles.

However, in some communities there might be restrictions to participation based on specific relevant criteria, for example, like working in a country or region, or expertise and experience with a particular topic, which may also include holding professional qualifications or job titles. In any case, the level of participation shown by participants is a matter of choice rather than a contractual obligation.

Communities, and the people who comprise them, can shape not only priorities of infrastructure, policy, and support, but also the development of Open Science.

Communities can also be spaces for a more radical approach in creating connections with people who share a common interest, like Open Data, but with different views to try to identify and fill gaps in knowledge or expertise.

3.3 Community

This starter kit is intended to provide potential and current community leads and members with information about approaches to community development, from planning through to expansion and sustainability.

It draws on the [Community of Practice](#) (Trayner and Trayner, 2015), Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CCSCE) [Community Participation Model](#) (Woodley and Pratt, 2020), and [Community Canvas](#) (2017a) model, to help establish a new community or enhance an existing one.

Professional communities aim to strengthen Open Science practices and research data sharing as members learn, exchange expertise, experiences, and collaborate to advance a field, build tools, work in projects, and act together to solve problems within their domains.

Moreover, as [Armeni](#) et al. (2021) argue, the initiatives and growth of Open Science is often built on small groups of innovators or early adopters coming together to do one or more of developing software, changing behaviours (such as encouraging data sharing), promoting knowledge, or providing training and support.

3.4 Communities and Networks

A starting point for thinking about a community is to identify the theory and models for establishing one. This will help shape the concept effectively by thinking about why you feel a community is needed, who would be involved, and how to organise one in such a way as to establish and grow it.

First, are you interested in a community or network? Despite being closely related, the concepts are not synonyms. The difference is in how people in these groups connect.

[Edersheim](#) (2021) makes the distinction based on chains of connection. Networks have loose, limited bonds between people. You may be connected to someone in a network but have little to do with someone else connected to the person to which you are connected. For example, you may know your neighbour, but do you know your neighbour's neighbour? Communities however are mutually supportive, and based on a purpose and intended to connect everyone in that community.

At its basic distillation: "Networks connect; communities care." But that may not mean communities and networks are mutually exclusive. Networks can have community elements, and communities can network. Nor does it mean that one is superior to the other. After all, you might not need to know your neighbour's neighbour.

Table 1 – Community v. Network

<i>Community</i>	<i>Network</i>
Exist for mutual support, cooperation, and accomplishing a goal	Primary uses are for finding a resource, learning, and disseminating information

Shared interest, values, goals, or mission	Open, no defining shared purpose necessary
Creates and perpetuates strong bonds	Consists of loose or bridging bonds
Has membership boundaries/Limited	Open/unlimited
Provide trust and support	Encourage cross-pollination of ideas
Characterized by shared purpose/ideas	Platform for new opportunities

Source: Edersheim (2021)

3.5 Introduction to Communities of Practice

In a review of the literature on Communities of Practice, [Schulte](#) (2021, pp. 48-49) concludes that they are understood as either theoretical lenses that explain a learning process, or organisational concepts that provide a place for education, innovation, and adaptability.

Our focus in this tool kit is with the organisational approach, that is avoiding explanations of how people learn within communities, and instead conceptualising the construction of an effective community.

A Community of Practice is a group "of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly" (Trayner and Trayner, 2015, p. 2).

Three elements produce and sustain a community:

1. Interaction: through prior, or building relationships, between participants by communication or collaborative activity.
2. A common domain of interest: Open Science, or elements of Open Science practice.
3. Shared experience: Directly sharing experiences, or using common tools, facing similar challenges, can all be part of this element.

You may already be part of a community without you, or the community, realising it. That may be through:

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- Profession: “We are all Data Librarians”
- Location: “We are all in...”

Or...

- Educational affiliation: “...at the University of...”

It could also be through occasional participation, for example, through mailing lists or voting in an election, or active membership in others, where you may hold an elected position, serve on committees, or work in advocacy.

Communities of Practice can be a retrospective term applied to existing communities, rather than purposive, for establishing new ones. They are not task groups, though they may involve tasks. They are not necessarily (or merely) groups of people with a common interest, for example, not all Data Scientists are in a Data Scientist Community of Practice unless those Data Scientists interact based on shared experience, problem solving, and learning.

For Trayner and Trayner (2015), a Community of Practice has three crucial characteristics:

1. Domain: An identity defined by shared interest, like Open Science, or elements like, for example, replication, reproducibility, meta research, data sharing, Open Access, Open Software, Open Hardware, Open Educational Resources, Open Data, Open Source. This implies commitment and shared competence and can be informal in terms of entry to that domain. For example, you don't need a PhD, or even an academic affiliation, to enter an Open Science community.
2. Community: Somewhere participants build relationships enabling learning with, and from, each other. Members should have some investment as to their standing in that community, for example, wanting to learn how to apply Open Science practices, like reproducibility, in their own work, and being able to demonstrate that learning.
3. Practice: Members as practitioners. They have a shared repertoire of resources, experiences, stories, tools, and ways of addressing problems. For Open Science, a community can include practitioners like researchers, but also research support who directly assist Open Science principles in

their work or develop and sustain infrastructure and resources that help this support.

Communities of Practice need not be limited by formal structures, organisations, or geography. They may or may not have an institutional or locative-defined aspect. They are, however, "organic". That is, there may be some organisation and leading positions, but it is not a formal, assigned, and hierarchical group organised for the purposes of completing a task.

[Mercieca](#) (2017, p. 5) argues that professional development, especially in a university setting has traditionally been "top-down" in delivery, through avenues like seminars and conferences, which, by their nature, tend towards passive engagement, offering limited avenues for engagement or ongoing discussion with experts. A Community of Practice is a different means of effecting learning and change, with active participation to share experiences, and space to develop practice. The results are institutional memory creation and helping overcome barriers of isolation, especially for less senior members of communities (Mercieca, 2017, p. 23).

3.6 Benefits of Communities

A combination of domain, community, and practice characteristics constitutes a Community of Practice, and they can develop in parallel through a variety of forms which provide a benefit to members, the community itself and wider community. Things a community can do, for example, include:

- Amplifying concerns: "We are worried about..."
- Building an argument: "How can we push back against the argument that..."
- Documenting: "How did we manage (or here's how others managed) to do something..."
- Identifying gaps: "There's no community that brings together Data Protection Officers and Repository managers."
- Problem solving: "How do we get researchers to share data?"
- Requesting information: "What kind of journal policies on data sharing are in place?"
- Reusing assets: "This is a great tool for making data FAIR..."

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- Seeking experience: “This person has managed to do...”
- Shaping own role: “What does it mean to be a...”
- Sharing opportunities: “Here’s a job at...”
- Visits: Going to learn from others.

Communities of Practice are not entirely self-organising, nor are they always collegial. Some may be more organic in coming together, but most will need some level of coordination and direction, and, of course, some decision making. Just being a good facilitator is not enough, you will also need to recognise the things that give value to participants in that community. That could just be knowledge sharing, but it can also be creating, developing, or organising a range of activities.

3.7 Responsibilities

Membership is often voluntary but here are responsibilities necessary for sustaining.

Two primary roles necessary to any community are lead(s) and champion(s). Leads guide and focus the community and champions, internally and externally. As suggested, these roles may be filled by more than one person working together as a team. Likewise, they are not exclusive, leads can champion, and champions can lead, as well as do other things in the community that contribute to its success.

What are some of those "other things" that could be contributed?

They can include:

- Information and knowledge management: Managing and organising information about the community and ensuring people can access that information or information referenced by the community.
- Facilitating meetings: making sure meetings remain focused and that participants get to contribute.
- Managing relationships: strengthening and building relationships, identifying, and recruiting new members, and helping them move to more active roles.

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- Subject matter expertise: knowledge relevant to the field or topic to a professionally recognised standard like a postgraduate or doctorate degree or gained through equivalent work experience.
- Information and communication technologies: finding, managing, and maintaining access to technology platforms to manage information and allow people to participate in the community.

The starter kit expands on these roles in [section 4](#) (launch) and [section 5](#) (sustain).

4 Launch

Key actions: cover planning purpose and structure, establishing management, communication systems and ground rules, promoting the community, hosting a kick-off, and maintaining engagement.

4.1 Practical actions: Launch

- **Review existing communities** to avoid duplication or identify potential partners. Would an existing forum be complimented by a community?
- **Identify a clear purpose and “domain of interest”**. Consider gap(s) to fill or need(s) to meet. What is likely to realistically attract interest in terms of topic and form? How will the world be worse off if this community does not exist?”
- **Use planning models** like [Community Canvas](#) to define identity, values, goals, metrics, roles, decision-making processes.
- **Define membership criteria**, a code of conduct, and core values like diversity and inclusion - what is inclusive and exclusionary, and how to create and maintain a safe environment.
- **Identify lead(s) and champion(s)** to provide direction and advocate for the community. The CSCCE [Community Participation Model](#) can help identify skill competences and gaps in leadership.
- **Establish communication channels** and information management systems and procedures, including document repository.
- **Plan regular interactions** to facilitate discussions and manage relationships.
- **Host a kick-off** meeting to agree on aims, elect leaders, set ground rules, and facilitate discussions.
- **Promote** through internal and external participation, materials, newsletter, social media, attending or organising conferences.
- **Recruit** members, enable contributions, and share opportunities to sustain engagement to maintain, grow, and evolve.

4.2 Getting going

Probably the most important decision is to create a community or not. Remember, the community needs a common domain, i.e. something that will define the identity of the group.

The Community Canvas model states: "a confident sense of identity builds the very core of a successful community and informs all other elements around it." (2017a, p. 6)

4.2.1 Defining Open Science

The [European Commission](#) (2018, p. 1) definition of Open Science, adopted for the EOSC in its glossary, is: "[An] approach to the scientific process based on cooperative work and ways of disseminating knowledge, improving accessibility to and re-usability of research outputs by using digital technologies and collaborative tools."

The [UNESCO](#) (2021, p. 7) definition of Open Science also includes these "key pillars" which is useful for scoping the kind of roles that could find a community useful: "open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems."

To build identity, the [Community Canvas](#) model asks why, and for whom, the community exists. It could be broad or niche; from Open Science and all it involves, through to a single aspect like reproducible methodology. It could be institutional - anyone interested in Open Science at specific research performing organisation or cross-institutional; localised - for example, a city; regional, national, or international - like the Research Data Alliance. It could be disciplinary or inter-disciplinary. It could be *anything*, but there needs to be *something*.

It could be that the something already exists, or doesn't need to exist. If so, the decision not to start a competing community can be just as valuable as deciding to start one. Indeed, the Community Canvas (2017c, p. 3) asks this directly: "How will the world be worse off if this community does not

exist/ceases to exist”? Creating a competing community could also lead to struggles with sustainability, and possibly affect the relevant domain negatively.

Even if you have got as far as reading this starter kit in thinking about a community, it may be the case that you conclude that a need does not exist or that it is already adequately met. Alternatively, what exists might not be a community, but a common domain gathering in a different form like an email list, discussion forum, informal social gathering, or social media hash tag (for example, #datalibs or #medlibs). In which case, a community might be an attractive, and complementary alternative.

You might, of course, have a good idea of what communities or gaps are in your domain of interest.

4.2.2 Radical Innovation

It’s also worth considering how far you want to take change and innovation. Finding the right approach here is a task of some importance. Talking about communities of practice as space for learning, [Wenger](#) (2010, p. 4) suggests that; “In such social systems, boundaries are interesting places. (...) At the same time, boundaries can be as much a source of learning as the core of a practice. The meetings of perspectives can be rich in new insights and radical innovations”.

This is further elaborated in terms of freedom from historical norms: “This is often only possible when communities interact with and explore other perspectives beyond their boundaries.” (Wenger 2010, p. 3).

However, Wenger does not refer to a definition of radical innovation. If you want to break away from incremental innovation in a domain, the framework provided by [Henderson and Clark](#) (1990) uses the term radical innovation to refer to changing both linkages between core concepts and components, and overturning core concepts. Otherwise, you will be creating either incremental innovation, architectural innovation, or modular innovation. Although this refers to product development, it is vital to think of who you should bring together.

4.3 Planning and preparation

Approaches to building, sustaining, and developing communities, like a Community of Practice, identify the need to have a domain of interest, a community, and common experiences. Finding something that could potentially satisfy all three is foundational to building a community.

As mentioned, you may already have experience of being in a community that you feel has a gap to fill in terms of knowledge, or would provide benefit from a different form of organisation.

The Community Canvas model (2017b) provides a "[Minimum Viable Community](#)" set of nine questions to help identify your community and how to approach its values, aims, and management. It ranges from the broad ("Why does the community exist?") through to some specifics ("In the next 12 months, what are three metrics that will define success for us?"), It also poses organisational questions on identifiable roles, selection, decision making, and communication channels. A more rigorous set of questions provided by the [Canvas](#) (2017c) can be used to follow-up on these initial ones.

From an Open Science perspective, Skills4EOOSC deliverable 6.1 might be a useful place to start scoping potential communities.

4.3.1 Skills4EOOSC Deliverable 6.1: Mapping of existing professional networks

Skills4EOOSC work package, [deliverable 6.1](#) (Buss et al., 2023a) mapped existing Open Science professional networks in 24 European countries. The task looked at professional Open Science networks in Skills4EOOSC countries to identify "credibility gaps" in network support.

There were some boundaries to what it examined, so hobby or commercial networks were not included. It only considered academic and research networks, and not networks in the private sector, commercial, or industry, and did not attempt to identify networks that might also be organised within projects, but not identifying itself as a community. Finally, its scope was

outside of networks in individual institutions, focusing only on collaborative ones. Yours, of course, need not be bounded this way.

The task found there was no registry of Open Science communities, or of the networks identified. It also found that life sciences dominated in disciplinary focus, and that, intuitively, nations with a small national number of networks have a less diverse range of networks.

Further findings relevant to professional networks were that most are relatively new. Furthermore, Open Science focused networks tended to be "bottom up", they start at the lowest levels and often with the activity of a few individuals aiming to provide solutions for a problem. In essence, networks were established to refine practices, develop expertise, and disseminate Open Science messages and training, particularly around topics such as FAIR data.

Data underpinning this deliverable is [available](#) (Buss et al., 2023b), which can help you identify networks on a country or topic basis. The data also include descriptions of networks, their purpose, and activities.

Something to keep in mind is that over time, and as membership (hopefully) grows, a community's aims and objectives can shift and evolve depending on the membership. Likewise, the community can dissolve if it feels the work it needed to do has been subsequently completed.

Topics that are best suited will be those that are "problematic"; the type of things that attract discussion; might not have a consensus view; are not easily solvable; or beyond that, have no clear starting point. If there is no current satisfactory way to share ideas, practices, discuss problems, or collaborate on addressing them, then there is probably space for a community. Establishing something around routine practice or settled knowledge is unlikely to attract interest.

4.3.2 Tacit knowledge

Thinking about the kind of knowledge in your community is also useful. Communities of Practice, for example, can also be beneficial where there is the aspect of tacit knowledge, but what is tacit knowledge? [Choo](#) (2002, pp.

79-80) talks of tacit kinds as a concept to explain that which is derived from practice and experience. It is the kind of knowledge that is hard to express and verbalise as it is practised through actions like intuition, hunches, heuristics, or workarounds, as ways of thinking about a problem.

4.4 Positionality, Charter, and Code of Conduct

Working on some kind of core set of documents that establishes what the community is for, who is eligible for involvement, as well as some objectives and targets, is not intended to be too proscriptive or ambitious, but it should help give shape and direction. This will help you and potential participants understand what it is about and if it would be of interest to them.

4.4.1 Positionality

Acknowledging that we see and experience in different ways is also something to consider building into the core of your community. This "positionality" approach ([Cousin](#), 2010, pp. 9-18), how our experiences and identity influence our world view, is important. Being aware of, listening, and communicating to others how our multiple positions relate to structures or systems of power, should be an ongoing practice. This helps us to understand our colleagues and communities.

Thinking about positionality is not only to practice an empathetic skill on a personal level, being able to anticipate someone else's response, like happiness or discomfort (important in managing a community), but also realising our place and impact in a professional community. Some questions to consider if trying to write this into a charter might be: how do our personal, professional, and intellectual positionality (the identities we are, contexts in which we live; the experiences we have, and perspectives we hold) inform, relate to, or diverge from others in our profession? It might be worth taking time to reflect on your own positions, like, for example this statement in 4.4.2 from [Gaynor et al.](#) (2022, p. 2):

4.4.2 Example of a positionality statement

Positionality and process statement

We are a team of researchers and data scientists across career stages based at the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS), an independent research affiliate of the University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB). Our group includes Masters of Environmental Data Science (MEDS) students, members of the NCEAS executive team, postdoctoral researchers, science communicators, and staff scientists. To develop these rules, we drew on our collective experiences conducting team-based data-intensive science. Individually and collectively, we reflected on when we have and have not felt a sense of belonging, and what actions have, and have not, fostered that feeling. Throughout the manuscript, we cite many actions that we have found to be impactful at NCEAS, and while our examples draw heavily from our own experiences, the general rules apply across research environments.

Our perspectives and senses of belonging are shaped, in large part, by our individual experiences. We all have access to higher education and research opportunities and are based at UCSB, a space that is exclusive and privileged. While we represent a diversity of backgrounds and identities, including some that have been largely excluded from science, our authorship team of course does not reflect the full diversity of human experiences.

How can we bring these positionalities together? The empathetic approach is to listen to others around questions of what is the community's imagined ideal professional understanding of what it should be, or do, and what are the implications of this understanding?

4.4.3 Code of Conduct

Related to this is thinking about a charter or code of conduct. A code is there to help maintain an environment, physically, virtually, or both, that can optimise participant involvement by creating a safe environment based on mutual respect.

The code can be founded values like equality, diversity, inclusion, recognising that our experiences are influenced by a multitude of intersectional factors ([D'Ignazio and Klein, 2020, pp. 3-4](#)), such as:

- Gender

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- Ethnicity and race
- Class
- Appearance
- Age
- National origin
- Religion
- Sexual orientation
- Differently abled

A code can help raise awareness in a way that helps all behave responsibly by setting boundaries, for example, a commitment to collaboration, expectations on privacy and confidentiality, for example, open (public) or closed (private) discussion.

A code can help particularly with guidance on behaviour that might be unconsciously or unintentionally aggressive or hostile, like microaggressions (Sue and Spanierman, 2020, pp. 7-9); but also with members who are explicitly rude, aggressive, intimidating, or exhibit a combination of unacceptable behaviours, by including procedures and sanctions for dealing with discriminatory or threatening actions.

Two examples to illustrate: 4.4.4 is from the [Research Data Access and Preservation Association](#) (2021), for behaviour in their community of a few hundred research data related people which meets and works remotely.

4.4.4 Extract from RDAP Code of Conduct Extract from RDAP Code of Conduct (Research Data Access and Preservation Association, 2021).

CODE OF CONDUCT

updated: 2021-11-22

The Research Data Access and Preservation (RDAP) Association is committed to providing an inclusive environment where all people can participate fully in all activities without fear of harassment or discriminatory behaviour toward them.

The below code of conduct seeks to provide examples of what this looks like in practice, as well as describe what actions the organisation will take when behaviours do not meet this standard.

This Code of Conduct applies to all spaces, both physical and virtual, managed by the RDAP Association, including but not limited to the Summit, workshops, social media, and community forums such as the email list. This Code of Conduct applies to all who attend and participate in an RDAP event, including RDAP members, non-members, and guests. Participation in any RDAP activity in any capacity is a privilege and indicates assent to this Code of Conduct.

Small actions you can take will help us meet this goal. With special thanks to the Digital Library Federation for this wording, we suggest the following actions:

- * listening as much as you speak, and remembering that colleagues may have expertise you are unaware of;
- * encouraging and yielding the floor to those whose viewpoints may be under-represented in a group;
- * using welcoming language, for instance by using an individual's stated pronouns and favoring gender-neutral collective nouns ("people," not "guys");
- * accepting critique graciously and offering it constructively;
- * giving credit where it is due;
- * seeking concrete ways to make physical spaces and online resources more universally accessible; and
- * staying alert, as Active Bystanders, to the welfare of those around you.

The other (4.4.5) is for a smaller group of research scientists located in a single institution ([Stier, 2019](#))

4.4.5 Extract from Stier Lab Code of Conduct (Stier, 2019).

We seek an energetic community that fosters a diverse and inclusive environment that promotes participation from all members of our community. We value each member of our community and seek an environment where all members of our community experience a positive education experience where members are unaffected by non-inclusive

behaviour. Everyone who participates in our lab is expected to show respect, kindness, and patience with all other members within the lab at all times.

Adrian Stier, as the head of the lab, and all members within the lab are dedicated to a harassment- and discrimination-free experience for everyone. Discrimination or harassment based on racial or ethnic background, citizenship status, religion (or lack thereof), political affiliation, gender identity/expression, sexual orientation, dis/ability status, appearance or body size will not be tolerated. We do not tolerate harassment or discrimination by and/or of members of our community in any form.

We are particularly motivated to support new and/or anxious collaborators, people who are looking to learn and develop their skills, and anyone who has experienced discrimination in the past.

To make clear what is expected, we ask all members of the community to conform to the following Code of Conduct.

All communication - online and in person - should be appropriate for a professional audience including people of many different backgrounds. Sexual or discriminatory language and imagery is not appropriate at any time.

Be kind to others. Do not insult or put down other contributors.

Behave professionally. Remember that harassment and sexist, racist, or exclusionary jokes are not appropriate.

Please make an effort to make an inclusive environment for everyone. Give everyone a chance to talk and an opportunity to contribute.

Bullying or cruelty of any kind will not be tolerated.

Watch out for microaggressions. Be aware that your actions can be hurtful to others or contribute to a negative environment even if you had no intent of harm. Listen. Offer a genuine apology. Commit to learning and doing better.

A SPECIAL NOTE: Your work in this lab will be publicly available and recorded permanently on github. Please conduct yourself accordingly.

One other notable point about 4.4.5 is it cites and acknowledges how it is built on the work and examples of others, which is also an approach that can be adopted by any new group. See what others have done; take what you need, adopt what you like, disregard what you don't, and give credit where it is due.

4.5 Leads

At a minimum, you will need leads and champions. These do not need to be an individual, though, they can be.

Summarising research on small group and team effectiveness, [Kozlowski and Ilgen](#) (2006) identify alignment of team processes with environmentally driven task demands as critical to effective working together.

Thinking about the team design, training, and leadership that shapes processes to enhance performance, is central to a well performing group.

Their definition of teams as individuals interacting towards a common goal based on relevant, interdependent tasks, roles, and responsibilities in a bounded and linked system that's part of a wider environment, is comparable with the terms we are using of community.

The focus of behaviour in initial stages is more on individual dynamics, dominated by role defining behaviour. In later stages, often once members have been socialised, team dynamics emerge as tasks are more focused and deadlines (potentially) loom.

Kozlowski and Ilgen's (2006) synthesis find leadership is important, but how its importance manifests vary. Leadership in interdependent tasks is critical but less so for independent tasks. But within that there are different types of leadership: transactional, focused on goals, rewards, their connection to effort; and transformational focused on the efficacy of the team and building team members beliefs in their collective efficacy. Whatever the style, investing in leadership training is of benefit to all kinds of teams.

Most people have an intuitive awareness of what "leadership" is and thus would tend to agree that "we know it when we see it". Consequently, "leadership" is not hard to recognise in a general sense, even if pinning a precise definition on the term is problematic. At its core, leadership appears to be the ability or process of one or a group of individuals to influence another individual or group into undertaking certain goals.

In a community, even small and informal ones, leadership will be those who help focus on task engagement and organisational aspects.

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The leadership role(s) provide the opportunity to set the agenda, so there is the chance to not only benefit from participation, but also gain a competitive advantage from influencing its goals, aims, and objectives.

From a practical stance, the CSCCE [Community Participation Model](#) (Woodley and Pratt, 2020) is intended to help communities develop once they have outlined what it is that the community should achieve, partly by conceptualising how it could work.

4.5.1 Skills Wheel

The model includes advice on facilitating and management roles in a community through something called the “skills wheel” (Fig. 1).

Fig.1 – CSCCE Skills Wheel

Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]

Skills are things which can develop by training ([Woodley et al., 2021, p. 8](#)). A skills wheel helps individuals and collectives by recognising skills required in a role to assist people in identifying objectives for professional development or allocate them elsewhere, and, at a broader level, support gap analyses of the skills across a community.

The skills wheel has five core competences:

- Interpersonal
- Programme management
- Programme development
- Communication
- Technical

A range of skills underpinning these. The emphasis on some skills over others depends on the context. If there is a disciplinary focus, familiarity with that discipline would be a useful skill; smaller communities may emphasise interpersonal skills.

Critically, be aware that competences may be more prominent in the launch - from a likely initial emphasis on programme development, content creation and technical, through to communication, management, and then interpersonal in more established groupings.

Finally, don't expect you or a person to be a master (or enjoy) all skills and competences. Look to share the burden inside or outside the community.

4.6 Champions

In the Community Participation Model is a role called “Champions” (Woodley and Pratt, 2021) where a member, or members, campaign on behalf of the group or for its objectives.

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The champion might have a formal role in a community, but this is not necessary. Some may have a formal status, others informal. They can help with:

1. Maintaining: These are activities that keep the community running, from doing things helping to welcome new members and helping members make connections, to working on internal administration, like document management.
2. Grow: Pushing the community in their own networks, helping craft messages and identify mediums for expanding awareness and membership.
3. Evolve: Helping the community move to the next stage. For example, helping craft strategic plans, reviewing aims and objectives, serving in executive roles.

All three types of champion role are significant in helping with the burden of management, giving it a legitimacy within a wider group, and helping to connect with local levels or future practitioners.

4.6.1 Membership Rewards

There are some things to think about when it comes to champions, and in fact any form of participation in a community.

In a field like academic research and research support where problems of “vocational awe” are real, i.e. oppression and exploitation ([Ettarh, 2018](#)), people should be rewarded in some form for their labour.

Likewise, regarding positionality, recognising the positionality of members of the wider community is an issue. Participation can be exploitative, but it can also be a privilege, particularly when voluntary activities can be used to enhance resumes and professional standing. Not everyone can provide the time to participate in communities outside of their core work. There are a range of reasons why not; family responsibilities, geography and time zones, ability to work at home, etc. So, keep in mind who is participating, but also who is not, and why that may be.

Assuming there is money, financial aspects can bring additional complications aside from sustainability, as well as burdens when it comes to administration. Trying to pay people outside of an organisation can be a nuisance, especially if they are resident in another tax jurisdiction. Furthermore if there is a legal dimension to a champion's work, which is likely apropos of GDPR and Codes of Conduct, that too would need to be considered.

Thinking about who you would need as champions, can the needs be met internally or is reaching out beyond familiar faces required? Related is the question of necessities: are there barriers to participation, would a selection process be needed, and, if so, how can that be transparent and inclusive?

4.7 Kick-off

So, when you have an area of interest identified, some leads, and champions, it's time to get started.

4.7.1 First meeting

A launch meeting, or "kick-off", is the chance to start gathering regularly to help forge an identity.

Choices about in person or online meetings are to be considered in the context of the nature of the group - for example, a geographically wide dispersal would be more attractive to host online; if your community happens to be more concentrated, in-person meetings might be better. Remember again to consider other peoples' circumstances. Are time-zones an issue? How about duplicating meetings? Is after work attractive for an in-person, accept not everyone is able to meet outside work hours.

If you are meeting online, make sure to test the hosting set-up so that it works.

What should you cover in that first meeting?

Ideally, focus on aims and objectives. You will have an idea of what they are, that is why you are launching a community, but some refinement and

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discussion, as well as what objectives might look like, is useful. This can take the form of discussion on the charter.

If there are things that you want people to read, make sure they have them in advance and can access them (for example, is an article paywalled?)

If there are topics you want to address, or questions you want to discuss, again, give notice so people can prepare and think about them.

4.7.2 Example kick-off meeting agenda

1. Welcome participants [Short period – a few minutes]

Objectives of meeting

Expectations around behaviour and conduct

2. Participant introductions [Short to medium period – 5 to 10 minutes, or longer]

3. Introduction to community and why it is needed. [Medium period – over 10 minutes]

Common domain

Introduction to theories and models

4. Aims and objectives: What do we want to achieve? [Long period – around the 30 minute mark]

Learn from each other?

Solve a problem?

5. How do we organise ourselves? [Long]

Identifying leadership and champions

Methods of communication and working

6. Summary of meeting: [Short]

Reiterate actions and next steps.

Timings depend on the size and nature of the group, but short items should be a few minutes long, medium around ten-fifteen minutes, and longer around thirty minutes plus.

Depending on the size and nature of the group, one important aim of a kick-off meeting is getting members to know each other better and build trust in one another to help cohesion and productivity. The “depending” aspect of this, and the reason it is tagged short to medium in terms of time allotted in the example presented in 4.7.2, is due to the size and existing familiarity of the group. It may be small and members already know each other, or it may be large and require more introductory time.

Another kick-off topic is identifying leadership within the group, if there is no paid manager position, and possibly incentives and mechanisms for attracting and selecting them - do you need to run elections if there is competition, for example?

Think also about facilitating discussions.

The [Community Canvas](#) (2017d, p. 6) found communities work best “when they have clear rules set in advance, so people know what their rights and expected responsibilities are.” It goes on to warn that “Decision making is best clarified in advance and helps avoid and address conflicts, a surprisingly common sight within many communities.”

Again, context matters. Online meetings can be partly moderated using tools, whereas in-person relies on stronger interpersonal skills.

The ability to do things like keep a focus on the objectives of the meeting, remind people of code of conduct requirements and expectations, help everyone who wants to contribute, and be able to sum up a discussion and identify any action points, are the facilitation skills needed whatever the format of the meeting. One useful question from the [Community Canvas](#) to consider in this respect is: “What is the existing digital behaviour of the members and how can the community integrate into that?” (2017c, p. 24). It might be that your core already has adopted channels, for example, Slack, that can be utilised by the community without much disruption or providing barriers to entry.

Some ways you can help facilitate a meeting:

4.7.3 Basic meeting facilitator responsibilities

1. Prepare in advance.

Advance preparation is a pre-requisite to effective facilitation of meetings. Think about who is attending (audience), what ideal outcomes are (reach a decision, solve a problem, learn something), why the meeting is happening (purpose), when it is happening (time and date), and where (physical location, online, or hybrid).

2. Plan an agenda and distribute it.

This helps prime attendees on the content and structure of meetings, and helps participants focus during meetings. Give people time to read the agenda and prepare.

3. State objectives at the start.

Again, this will create a focus around what needs to be accomplished by the meeting. What is the intended outcome(s)? Even if the content of those outcomes is something to be determined by the meeting.

4. State, refer, or remind people of behaviour expectations.

Whether to state, refer, or remind depends on an assessment of the size, nature, and familiarity within the group. But doing one of these at the start to remind participants there is a code of conduct and expectations around interactions within the meeting helps reinforce respect and helps collaboration.

5. Guide inclusivity.

Again, how this is done can vary, and an appropriate way depends on the nature of the meeting, but good facilitation should make all feel included. Not everyone needs to speak, but no one should feel they cannot.

6. Provide closure and reiterate action items.

Be prepared to sum up the meeting, especially any action points or follow-up items, and who has responsibility for them.

4.7.4 Promotion

The other main kick-off task is to consider how the community will be promoted. How can you get the message to people that would be interested or of value?

- Discussion forums (email, Slack, Discord)
- Producing material, which can range from promotional to research articles.
- Newsletter
- Social media accounts
- Targeting conferences at which to present, or even organising your own.

All the above are actions intended to sustain your community.

5 Sustain

Key actions: facilitating participation, incentivised engagement, adjusting programming, managing transitions, ensuring sustainability, and addressing group behaviour pitfalls.

5.1 Practical actions: Sustain

- **Anticipate group development stages** like convey/consume, contribute, collaborate, co-create. Roles and dynamics will evolve.
- **Provide "scaffolding" to overcome participation barriers** like a lack of information, technical support, and sense of belonging. This can include things like welcoming new members, surveys, social events, technical guides, templates, and promotional materials.
- **Member engagement.** Recognise and make use of different levels of participation from core to peripheral. Avoid having too static of membership in terms of engagement.
- **Manage transitions:** Have onboarding and offboarding processes. Onboarding welcomes new members and sets expectations. Offboarding recognizes contributions.
- **Reflect on aims, satisfaction,** and adjust programming and engagement approaches as needed. Adjust activities and focus based on what members are asking for and problems arising.
- **Provide value** through things like networking, enhancing profiles, and learning opportunities. Make the case for participating.
- Have processes for **succession and transferring knowledge.**
- **Consider team roles and behaviours.** frameworks like Belbin help identify roles and behaviours and their strengths and weaknesses.
- **Be aware of potential group dynamic issues** like social loafing, free riding, groupthink, group polarisation, and common knowledge effect. Have strategies to counteract these.

In this section we look at sustaining a membership and building relationships to move to its next stages.

Having launched, it is important to think about sustaining and growing membership to help achieve your aims and objectives. As the [Community Canvas](#) (2017d, p.6) cautions, “Visionary communities will put structures in place that will optimize for long-term stability”.

Of course, this is not a corporate hierarchy. Membership is, most likely, voluntary, so activity is based on goodwill, enthusiasm, and passion.

This section uses the Community Participation Model to try and understand what might be happening in your community.

5.2 Membership

The nature of the community will likely change over time. This is a finding borne out in knowledge management research. As long ago as the 1960s, Tuckman (1965) reviewed the then existent leadership on teamwork, and as a result, talked about a set of sequential stages of development.

5.2.1 Development

It starts with:

- **Forming:** Tasks we discussed in setting up, and participants get to know each other and find out acceptable behaviours. This stage is characterized by high uncertainty, politeness, and low levels of commitment. Here an “authority” figure critical to helping define boundaries and behaviours.
- **Storming:** Cliques start to form with some jostling for position in the group as roles begin to clarify. It is a stage characterized by intra-group conflict.
- **Norming:** Group norms start to emerge, and divergent views are addressed one way or the other. At this stage trust and cohesion amongst people starts to surface.
- **Performing:** Now people are working together as a coordinated, mature group, characterized by flexible and functional interactions, and actively producing work.

A contemporary take on this, and from a community perspective is in the CSCCE [Community Participation Model](#) (Woodley and Pratt, 2020). We can take their levels of modes and “slogan” to introduce this point.

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The model has four kinds of mode with an associated slogan, and we can apply them to hypothetical Open Science examples as illustrations of the various stages a community may go through.

- Convey/Consume: “Here’s something interesting”.

Is there a need to tell people something? Are you thinking your group will be focused on people who need information imparted to them, often from a small number of community leads? For example, *this will allow me or my colleague to tell people who know nothing or little about Open Science what it is and what are the benefits*. In which case, do you imagine people will be able to passively receive information by listening, reading, or watching, while you or your colleagues, as the experts, are informing and inspiring the next generation of open researchers? Given the nature of this mode, broadcast tools would be an appropriate medium for transmitting information. Preferably, low barrier ones with an emphasis less on interaction, and more on projecting. Mediums such as social media, a blog, or even email can work in this context.

- Contribute: “Give us some feedback”.

Is there a need for people to tell you something? This would be focused on people who have information to contribute to your community. This could, for example, be useful in a policy-related exercise. For example, *how do we get researchers to deposit data in a repository or archive?* Then researchers might comment based on experience, citing obstacles like “data sensitivity”, “fear of being scooped”, “time”, “too difficult to do”, “don’t believe in it”, and so on. They might be survey participants selecting predefined categories on obstacles to data sharing in repositories, so you may find that 20 percent of respondents believe “data sensitivity” is an obstacle to sharing. Other times this approach might be useful to identify community participants - who do you know that practices Open Science? Let the community know, we might be able to facilitate connection. Your or your colleagues are managing feedback, skills, insights, and information. Communication infrastructure in this mode can be like those in the “Convey/Consume” mode, but with the direction of communication switched from transmit to receive.

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- Collaborate: “How can we work together?”

Is there a need for us to learn together? This is a cooperative type, with information flowing from leads to members, but also flowing to members to leads. The “hands on” attitude in the preceding slogans are becoming more “hands off”. For example, learning about Open Science, or an aspect of Open Science, like appropriate licensing of research data for reuse. Sharing information on licence templates; discussing their appropriateness in different contexts; working together to produce guidance shared on that exchange of knowledge, and helping participants to overcome barriers to cooperation are all examples. Given this mode breaks from the one-to-one nature outlined in the conveying and contributing modes, additional features that facilitate collaboration are needed. Google docs, Slack, Teams, Zoom could all be useful tools here.

- Co-Create: “What shall we do next”?

This slogan suggests information can be used in a transformational type, not hierarchical, as the other slogans suggest to varying extents, but a convergent working together to share information and create something on a basis of informed understanding that they would not have been able to do previously. That may be an article, a teaching resource, or it may be a policy, a conference, or other kind of event. The highly interactive nature of this mode requires the same type of tools as collaborating, but possibly on a larger scale, especially if working groups and training is involved. We may also be at the stage of formally organised events, in which case the resources required for in-person events, i.e. logistical and financial, will also need consideration.

It is not the case that these slogans signify mutually exclusive stages or types. They might progress through these modes of participation, but they could even be two, three or four types at once. It is more likely a group starts off saying “here is something interesting”. Furthermore, the authors of the CSCCE model state that co-creating are not an end goal for all. “Success” is dependent on goals and the satisfaction of its participants, not metrics on outputs or engagement (Woodley and Pratt, 2020, p. 9).

5.3 Participation

The other main component of the CSCCE model is “Scaffolding”. This is “Supportive information, activities, and processes that address barriers to member participation” ([Woodley, et al., 2022, p. 6](#)). Some of these barriers can be due to structure, and others due to individual behaviours.

The CSCCE model identifies lack of information, technical support, and sense of belonging as barriers which can be overcome by scaffolding. It is effective in the contribute mode, which itself is built around participation and engagement, and critical to collaborative and creative work. So, what kinds of activities are scaffolding activities?

- Welcoming new members with concise information points about the community
- Surveying members to keep in touch of member needs and contribution preferences.
- Social events, either one-to-one or small group: These need not be in person.
- Technical support: A guide to using platforms. How do you get started with Slack, Discord etc. if you have never used them before?
- Templates for slides, note taking, and organisation groups: Ways to set up clear and consistent documentation, branding, and reinforcing community norms.
- Promotional material: to attract new members, for example, postcards that can be handed out at conferences as a means of attracting new members.

Keep in mind that participation is voluntary. People will be providing their time and effort because they want to, and there may be different motivations for that, like idealism, passion, or career advancement. Consequently, there is a bit of a balancing requirement between harnessing commitment to participate with providing value in return.

This can cover different aspects:

- Enhancing profile: networking and connecting with experts.

- Learning and training: using connections and exposure to enhance their own skills and experiences.

Remember, this can apply to participants, but equally to employers who may want to see a return on time spent, or membership fees required for participation. These may not always be obvious, and it can be to your advantage to highlight these points and assist current or potential members in making a case for participating.

5.3.1 Levels of Participation

The Communities of Practice model ([Wegner-Trayner, 2015](#)) accounts for different levels of participation, identifying five categories of participants:

1. Core group: leadership.
2. Active: practitioners who define the community.
3. Occasional: contribute when they have, or feel they have, something specific to contribute.
4. Peripheral: less engaged, either through being new, or unable to provide stronger commitment to participation.
5. Transactional: individuals outside the group, who might interact intermittently either to provide a contribution, or to benefit from the community's work.

As with other aspects of community development, there's no homogeneous state of membership. People will fall into different categories and will move between categories. Indeed, it is healthy and essential that they move, either naturally or through invitation. A static community is likely to stagnate. Although this does not apply to all. For example, a records manager being involved in a RDM group to provide insight into retention schedules can be seen as a transactional participant - they would not want or expect to be anything more.

Furthermore, having people on the periphery is not a bad thing. Indeed, the Community Canvas asks (2017c, p. 18): "How does the community deal with inactive members?" which can be answered with a neutral response: It doesn't.

However, it is a question of balance. A large periphery, leaving the burden of effort at the core, is not desirable. But marginalising the periphery is a problem, especially where intersectional barriers prevent greater activity.

5.3.2 Personality obstacles

There are other kinds of personality obstacles and problems that can arise, depending on size, nature, and task goals. Some identified by social psychology and management theory to consider include:

- “Social loafing”: Where individuals work less hard in a group by relying on the efforts of others, than they would do as individuals ([Karau and Williams, 1993, p. 681](#)). Partly addressed through emphasising the importance of individual efforts to outcomes and communication, particularly from leading members of the group, that enhances perceptions of importance and responsibility.
- “Free riding”: The problem of rationally motivated individuals not paying the cost of contributing yet deriving benefits from its work (Olsen, 1971, p. 11). The consequences of this are that a level of collective benefit is likely to be sub-optimal, unless special conditions exist, such as a motivated interest or group enthusiasm. Groups with “large” members are more likely to have a level of benefit for that group and its interests than groups with “small members” in terms of status and impact. Yet groups with few members are likely to avoid free riding to secure collective goods than groups with many members. However, groups will be more likely to solve their collective action problem over time, if they have time.
- “Groupthink”: Where group pressures and a desire for collegiality result in “a deterioration of mental efficiency, reality testing, and moral judgement” (Janis, 1982, p. 12). Community leaders should be wary of using power or prestige to influence groups instead of encouraging open enquiry and critical evaluation (Janis, 1982, p. 176), particularly when a group is of similar age, background, ideology, and outlook (Janis, 1982, p. 244).
- “Group polarisation”: A consensus towards attitudes more extreme than those of its members as individuals - either as result of the discussion itself,

or out of a desire for consensus or favourable evaluation (Turner, et al., 1993).

- “Common knowledge effect”: A tendency that information common to a group prior to a discussion will more strongly influence the group’s subsequent discussion and judgment than new information. ([Gigone and Hastie](#), 1993, p. 160).

We have talked about roles, but so far we have not said much about the type of people involved.

5.3.3 Personality types

In management, the Belbin Team Role theory identified a balance of eight behaviours as critical to success or failure (Belbin, 2010, pp. 43-46; pp. 65-74). This was based on formal teams working in private companies, but it is worth being aware of the different types of people and finding ways to facilitate the best from them.

In the Belbin schema, people can represent more than one role, and they may have roles they prefer (“I’m happy to...”), ones they can manage (“well, if no one else wants to...”), and those they don’t want (“I’m not comfortable...”). Those eight behaviours are:

- “Plant”: A creative and unconventional problem solver.
- Monitor Evaluator: Logical eye, capable of impartial judgements, good at identifying options.
- Co-ordinators: Help focus on objectives, inclusive team members, and good at delegating.
- Resource Investigators: Have inside knowledge and are well connected to wider networks.
- Implementers: Help plan and deliver practical, workable strategies
- Completer Finishers: Good at quality control.
- Team workers: Supportive and sociable members.
- Shapers: Provide drive, keep things moving, and provide focus and momentum.

It's not essential to have every role represented, as there is scope for "allowable weakness" where absence is ideally covered by another role.

Again, not all of these may be necessary, but working out what is necessary is partly a reflection of asking which activity or behaviour you are most interested in supporting. For starting new communities, welcoming new members, and identifying and setting up platforms are likely essential. But there is also an iterative aspect, what are members saying or asking for? Do consistent problems arise? What are the obstacles that require scaffolding to overcome?

5.4 "Onboarding", or saying hello.

[Community Canvas](#) (2017a, p. 25) highlight how important the welcoming of new members is to a successful community, and provide some elements to help with an effective onboarding. Their main lesson: "as personal as possible: A call or face-to-face" over just an email.

Other stages Community Canvas suggest relating to some of the things we have looked at already in this toolkit. This includes, creating a welcoming and safe environment, which in practice includes familiarising them with the community's purpose (why it exists), and culture around rules and expectations (organisation, charter, conduct, positionality). This includes levels of expectation around their involvement (what expectations of them are in terms of contributions), allied to ways to facilitate that involvement (what steps they can take to become involved and contribute). A "buddy" or "mentor" where a new member is paired with an existing one can help for larger communities.

5.5 "Offboarding", or saying goodbye.

Then, there is an end. All things end, and at some point, champions will move on, either voluntarily, or limited by terms. Therefore, the final stages include "offboarding" to recognise contributions and exchange knowledge, through an evaluation stage, and possibly to keep a level of involvement for the future.

The [Community Canvas](#) worksheet (2017c, p.12) is useful in the questions it asks to help address this stage. Is there an exit process? Either a formal resignation path, or a lapse in subscriptions, or a period of inactivity? Is there a separate structure or experience for people who have left, like an alumni community or honorary titles (for example, past president).

Consider also that there may be an end point for the community. Remember, we talked about identifying a need, and specifying some aims and objectives. If that need is felt to be no longer relevant, either through explicit statements to that effect, or by indirect signs like low attendance, a lack of interest in participating; or if those aims and objectives have been satisfied, then that might be an end.

5.6 Case studies

Finally, to tie what we have looked at together, and illustrate how it can be applied in practice, 5.6.1 and 5.6.2 present case studies of Open Science communities. Remember though, these are just examples to illustrate how the things outlined in this document can be found in an existing group, not something you feel yours should aspire towards or be compared against.

5.6.1 Case study: Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN)

The [Flemish Research Data Network](#) (FRDN) (n.d.) was established in 2019. The network features 36 research performing institution partners in the Flanders region of Belgium collaborating on Open and FAIR data.

Individual members comprise of research data professionals, including data stewards, library and research coordination staff, Open Science policy officers, ICT staff, and researchers committed to Open Science.

The network itself has a stated vision (exchanging FAIR data and metadata), mission (support implementation of Flemish Open Science policy), and set of values (professionalism, collaboration, inclusivity, transparency, and research-orientated). It locates itself in the context of EOSC.

Although not a bottom-up network, it is supported by the Flanders regional government, it does foster a self-learning community for research support

staff called "The Knowledge Hub", which uses Basecamp as an information and discussion platform, and hosting monthly seminars based on suggestions from the community with published summaries in the form of blog posts. This hub is supported by a content manager.

5.6.2 Case study: rOpenSci

Founded in 2011, [rOpenSci](#) (LaZerte et al., 2022) identifies as a community built around users of the R programming language and how it supports concepts of open and reproducible research.

There are no barriers to entry, other than an interest in developing or just using R software tools in an open context, with a community goal "to build confidence and a sense of belonging for people of all backgrounds. Particularly for those who might not see themselves as software developers."

To help onboarding and scaffolding, the community outlines various pathways based on participants' interests, and incentives, including self-interest like contributing to furnish your resume. These pathways are targeted to forms or channels of participation, such as attending meetings, or contributing reviews.

These paths include discovering data, tools, software, and good practices, being part of a supportive community, as well as improving and promoting Open Science

Acknowledgement is made that participation is "likely to be a lifecycle than a linear path", and at some point, the value of participation may no longer be there for some.

As a community emphasis is placed on a set of values integral to that community idea - not just things like openness and transparency in research and development, but also within that community. So specific mention is made of welcoming all backgrounds, inclusive of sexuality, gender identity, and race. To help deliver that commitment, the community has a Code of Conduct, and a Community Manager, while profiles of people with formal and informal community roles are provided for transparency, but also to "help people 'recognize themselves' in some roles".

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In relation to this, the community positions itself alongside other groups and organisations, like R-Ladies, The Carpentries, Latin American R community, the MiR community for under-represented minority users of R, AfricaR, and Bioconductor.

Communication in the community comes in many forms; some direct, some indirect. Indirect forms include using code and documentation. Some passive forms are blogs, talks, and webinars. Direct experiences come from coding clubs, hacky hours, meet-ups, workshops, and conferences (or unconferences). Active online channels are social media.

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No	Description/Link
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R5	Community Canvas (2017a) Guidebook https://github.com/communitycanvas/documents/blob/master/CommunityCanvas-Guidebook.pdf
R6	Community Canvas (2017b) Minimum Viable Community https://github.com/communitycanvas/documents/blob/master/CommunityCanvas-MinimumViableCommunity.pdf
R7	Community Canvas (2017c) Worksheet https://github.com/communitycanvas/documents/raw/master/CommunityCanvas-Worksheet-Doc.pdf

R8	Community Canvas (2017d) Summary https://github.com/communitycanvas/documents/blob/master/CommunityCanvas-Summary.pdf
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